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Revenue Generation and Utilisation in Nigeria's Public Sector

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ABSTRACT

This study examined revenue generation and its utilisation in Nigeria's public sector. The study specifically focused on oil and non-oil revenue effects on social and community services expenditure. The study adopted the ex post facto research design and data were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, spanning from 1999-2022. The unit root test using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) showed stationarity at 1(0), 1(1), and 1(2). The hypotheses were tested using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. Interestingly, the results showed that oil revenue had a non-significant positive effect on social and community services; while non-oil revenue showed a non-significant negative effect on social and community services. The ARDL Bounds Test suggest that there is no strong evidence of a long-term cointegrating relationship between SOCS and the independent variables (OREV, NOREV, REER, and INFL). From these findings, the study recommends diversification of revenue sources beyond oil to reduce dependency on volatile oil prices. Secondly, enhancing transparency and accountability in the management of oil revenues to prevent misappropriation and ensure that funds are allocated efficiently to priority areas. Lastly, strengthening tax collection mechanisms and combatting tax evasion are essential to maximize non-oil revenue mobilization. Utilizing digital tax platforms, streamlining tax procedures, and enforcing compliance measures can boost government revenue streams to support social welfare initiatives.

Keywords: Oil Revenue, Non-Oil Revenue, Social and Community Services.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's public sector is characterized by its complexity and diversity, influenced by factors such as its colonial history, rapid population growth, and abundance of natural resources (Onwuegbuna & Abodunrin, 2024). The country's revenue generation and utilization practices have been shaped by these historical legacies. The public sector functions within an intricate political environment, with a system that consists of three levels of governance. This has implications for the generation and allocation of funds, as different levels of government have varying degrees of responsibility and control over financial management. However, revenue generation is heavily dependent on two main sources, first from natural

resources, especially oil and second from non-oil sources, e.g., tax (Oyedokun, Adeleye, & Nwabuzor, 2024). The revenue generated is used to fund the majority of the government's expenses, especially necessities like healthcare infrastructure that contribute to a healthy population and economic growth. Mobilizing and generating revenue is essential for countries to secure adequate funds (Oyedokun, Adeleye, & Nwabuzor, 2024).

Nigeria heavily depends on revenue generated from oil exports, however, the fluctuation of worldwide oil prices, along with the environmental and social consequences of oil extraction, have a substantial impact on how revenue is generated and utilized in the public sector (Oyedokun, Adeleye, & Nwabuzor, 2024). Nevertheless, there have been initiatives to broaden the revenue stream by boosting non-oil sources such as taxes, customs duties, and fees. In addition, tax revenue is the primary source of non-oil government income, so it is imperative to prioritize it (Umar-Dauda & Oyedokun, 2018). To address the country's expanding social and community services deficit, the government must generate adequate tax revenue. Unfortunately, the tax revenue collected over the years has consistently fallen short in addressing the increasing social and community services deficit, and in promoting economic growth.

During the colonial era, Nigeria's economic structure was primarily structured to benefit the interests of the colonial powers. This has had a long-lasting effect on the country's revenue generation and utilization practices, with important implications for current challenges in this area field. In the first half of 2021, the Nigerian government raised approximately 398 billion Nigerian naira (NGN) in internal revenue, equivalent to around 958 million U.S. dollars (Statista, 2023). In 2020, an Internally Generated Revenue (IGR) of over 1.3 trillion NGN, approximately 3.1 billion U.S. dollars, was recorded. Thus, having a robust tax system that is efficient, transparent, and fair is essential. Improving tax compliance, broadening the tax base, and reducing leaks are also critical elements. Furthermore, improved coordination and cooperation among various government agencies are necessary to enhance overall revenue generation endeavours.

According to Okoro (2013), the correlation between government spending and economic growth remains a topic of ongoing debate among scholars. The government serves two main functions - providing protection and security, as well as offering certain public goods (Al-Yousif 2000). Despite the plethora of studies on revenue generation and utilization in the Nigerian context, this study focuses on the specific effects of these financial practices on social and community services. Government revenue is derived from both oil and non-oil sources, including tax revenue, fines, and other fees. These revenues have been the pedestal of the country's development, and understanding their impact on social and community services is crucial for informed policy-making. Social and community services play a vital role in addressing socio-economic challenges and promoting equal access to opportunities for all citizens (Ebimngbo *et al.*, 2022). Quality healthcare services, education, and social welfare programs are key to improving the overall well-being and quality of life of the population (Abdulraheem, Olapipo, & Amodu, 2012; Oladeji, 2011). Thus, efforts to enhance social and community services should prioritize enhancing the accessibility, affordability, and quality of these services. This could entail investment in infrastructure, healthcare facilities, schools, and social support programs, along with training and capacity-building for service providers.

Against this backdrop, the specific objectives of the study are:

1. To determine the effect of oil revenue on social and community services expenditure.
2. To examine the effect of non-oil revenue on social and community services expenditure.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Revenue Generation

Revenue refers to the growth in financial resources of an individual or entity resulting from business transactions (Onwuegbuna & Abodunrin, 2024). According to the 1999 constitution, revenue encompasses all income or profits accruing to the government from the sale of assets, dividends from

stocks, loans, or any other related sources from a commercial establishment as specified by the constitution (Alao, 2013).

The government and its federating units use the revenues they generate to meet infrastructure and developmental needs. These revenues usually come from taxes, fees, rents, loans, dues, rates, and statutory allocations from the government, which help to increase the net worth of government units.

2.1.1.1 Oil Revenue

This refers to the income that the government of Nigeria earns from the exploration, production, and export of petroleum and its derivatives. It includes proceeds from crude oil sales, petroleum profit tax, royalties, and rents from oil companies. Nigeria is one of the largest oil producers in Africa and has been heavily reliant on oil revenue for its economic development. The discovery of oil in Oloibiri in 1956 marked the beginning of Nigeria's transformation into an oil-dependent economy. Oil revenue has significantly shaped the nation's fiscal policies and economic direction.

However, this heavy dependence has also exposed the country to the volatility of the global oil market, leading to economic instability during periods of low oil prices. The sharp decline in oil prices in 2014-2016 led to a severe economic recession in Nigeria. This period underscored the urgent need to diversify the economy and reduce dependence on oil revenue. The government, under President Muhammadu Buhari, launched the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP) in 2017, focusing on economic diversification, including improving non-oil revenue.

2.1.1.2 Non-Oil Revenue

This encompasses all other sources of government income apart from oil. The non-oil sector encompasses trade and industry outside of the oil and gas industry, playing a critical role in the Nigerian economy (Ude & Agodi, 2014). Key components include taxes (personal income tax, corporate tax, value-added tax), customs duties, excise duties, fines, fees, and other non-tax revenues like grants and aids.

In the Nigerian context, the non-oil revenue sector has historically been underdeveloped with the dominance of oil overshadowing efforts to diversify the revenue base. Nevertheless, there have been periods where the government has made concerted efforts to boost non-oil revenue, particularly in response to declining oil prices or production challenges.

2.1.2 Social and Community Service

Social and community services are essential for promoting the well-being, inclusivity, and overall development of a society. These services cover a broad spectrum of activities and programs designed to assist individuals and communities in various facets of their lives (Valaitis *et al.*, 2017). The social and community services sector encompasses services that are essential and cannot be denied to individuals who do not pay for them, such as street lighting. These services benefit society as a whole, rather than just the individual user, such as public education and health services (Ihugba & Njoku, 2017). Additionally, this sector includes services that promote equal opportunities, as well as services tailored towards individuals who are socially or economically disadvantaged, or have specific care and support needs. Key examples include healthcare, education, housing assistance, social welfare programs, mental health services, and support for vulnerable populations like the elderly and disabled (Low, Yap, & Brodaty, 2011; Udu & Onwe, 2016). Social and community services is not just a social responsibility, but also a strategic investment in the country's human capital and long-term prosperity.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Resource Mobilisation Theory (RMT)

RMT was developed by sociologists John D. McCarthy and Mayer N. Zald in the 1970s. A seminal article published in 1977 titled "Resource Mobilization and Social Movements: A Partial Theory" laid the foundation for the theory. RMT is a framework in sociology that outlines how social movements gather and utilize resources to achieve their goals. The theory explains social movements and collective action as a result of the strategic mobilization of resources such as money, labour, skills, and organizational structure. The theory suggests that successful social movements can effectively gather and utilize resources to achieve their goals. According to resource mobilization theory, social movements must

develop the necessary resources to sustain and carry out their activities, including creating networks of support, attracting financial donations, gaining access to media channels, and building alliances with other groups or organizations.

2.3 Empirical Review

Onwuegbuna and Abodunrin (2024) investigated the correlation between revenue generation and rural development in the Ado-Odo Ota LGA of Ogun State, Nigeria. The study assessed revenue generation using internally generated revenue (IGR) and federal allocation and measured rural development through capital expenditures during the specified time frame. The secondary data was obtained from the statutory allocation records, IGR documents, and official records on annual budgetary allocation from Ado-Odo Ota over the ten years from 2011 to 2020. The Pearson correlation analysis revealed no significant positive association between Federal Allocation and Capital Expenditure.

Oyedokun, Adeleye, and Nwabuzor (2024) investigated the relationship between tax revenue and infrastructure development in the healthcare sector of Nigeria. The study utilized an ex post facto research design and secondary data on tax revenue collected from Corporate Income Tax (CIT), Personal Income Tax (PIT), Excise Duty Tax (EDT), and Value Added Tax (VAT) from 2013 to 2021. The results indicate a strong positive correlation between spending on health infrastructure development and CIT, PPT, and VAT. Additionally, there is a positive non-significant relationship between EDT and infrastructure development in the healthcare sector.

Oghuma, Eluyela, and Iyoha (2022) analyze the relationship between non-oil taxes and economic growth in Nigeria. The study used secondary data from 1994 to 2019 from CBN was utilized for this research. The ARDL was used for model estimation. The long-run analysis revealed that non-oil taxes have an impact on economic growth. Conversely, the analysis showed a positive impact of capital expenditure on economic growth.

Ogunbiyi and Abina (2019) conducted a study to analyze the impact of non-oil revenue on development indicators in Nigeria. They utilised annual data from 1981 to 2018 analysed using time-series estimation techniques including the Unit Root test, Johansen Co-integration, and Error Correction Estimation. The analytical results showed no significant effect of non-oil revenue on the human development index.

Ogba *et al.* (2018) analyzed the impact of non-oil revenue on economic growth in Nigeria, specifically focusing on sectors outside of the oil industry. The data spanned from 1985 to 2017, and the regression analysis revealed a significant long-term relationship between Services Revenue Contribution (SRC), Agricultural Revenue Contribution (ARC), Manufacturing Revenue Contribution (MRC), and economic growth in Nigeria. Nevertheless, it was observed that the Solid Minerals Revenue Contribution (SMRC) had a negative impact. The Error Correction coefficient suggested a rapid return to equilibrium in cases of displacement, with an adjustment speed of 80% per year.

Ihugba and Njoku (2017) examined the effect of total government expenditure on social and community services and its impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The study utilizes time series data from 1961 to 2013 sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Annual Report and Statement of Account. Through the use of an error correction model (ECM), the findings suggest that government expenditure on social and community services has a positive relationship with economic growth in the long run, while in the short run, total expenditure on social and community services is highly and statistically significant and has a positive relationship on economic growth in Nigeria.

Aregbeyen and Kolawole (2015) analyzed the correlations between oil revenue, government spending, and economic growth in Nigeria. They used time series data from 1980 to 2012 analysed using econometric techniques, such as OLS, cointegration, VECM, and Granger causality. The results indicated that oil revenue Granger caused both total government spending and growth, whereas there was no causality observed between government spending and growth in the country.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The research employs a longitudinal research design to investigate the relationship between government revenue and social and community services expenditure in Nigeria. The data for the study were obtained from the annual statistical bulletin published by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and covered the years 1999-2022. This time frame was chosen to ensure there was no missing data.

3.1 Methods of Data Analysis

The study conducts a unit root test and, for robustness, utilizes the Dickey-Fuller, Augmented Dickey-Fuller, and Philip-Perron Tests. However, as similar results were obtained from DF and P-P, the researchers presented ADF for brevity. The cointegration test include the Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace and Maximum Eigenvalue). These tests help determine the number of cointegrating equations, which represent the long-term relationships between the variables.

3.1.1 Model Specification

Our model is specified according to the hypothesis.

$$SOCS = f(OREV, NOREV, REER, INFL) \dots\dots\dots Eq. (1)$$

Where: SOCS is the total government expenditure on social and community services, OREV is the total oil revenue, NOREV is the total non-oil revenue, REER is the real effective exchange rate, INFL is the inflation rate.

The ARDL model equation form for the dependent variable can be written based on the selected ARDL model.

The general ARDL model can be represented as:

$$SOCS_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SOCS_{t-1} + \beta_2 OREV_t + \beta_3 OREV_{t-1} + \beta_4 NOREV_t + \beta_5 NOREV_{t-1} + \beta_6 REER_t + \beta_7 INFL_t + \epsilon_t \dots\dots\dots Eq. (2)$$

Where:

- SOCS_t is the dependent variable (social and community services expenditure) at time *t*
- OREV_t is the oil revenue at time *t*
- NOREV_t is the non-oil revenue at time *t*
- REER_t is the real effective exchange rate at time *t*
- INFL_t is the inflation rate at time *t*
- β₀ is the intercept (constant term)
- β₁₋₇ are the coefficients for the respective variables
- ε_t is the error term at time *t*

4.0 Data Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of the model variables

	SOCS	OREV	NOREV	REER	INFL
Mean	659.4071	4527.048	2518.912	92.46495	13.07171
Median	774.7662	4462.910	2237.877	85.13346	12.00000
Maximum	1628.990	8878.970	7944.561	155.7536	23.80000
Minimum	79.63041	1230.851	314.4839	58.24839	6.600000
Std. Dev.	502.3108	2015.703	1997.386	27.06612	4.293781
Skewness	0.489030	0.284442	1.027539	1.140774	0.784913
Kurtosis	2.051157	2.558224	3.629935	3.302999	3.212356
Jarque-Bera	1.779536	0.497180	4.427658	5.076551	2.404888
Probability	0.410751	0.779900	0.109281	0.079003	0.300459
Sum	15166.36	104122.1	57934.99	2126.694	300.6493
Sum Sq. Dev.	5550956.	89387276	87770139	16116.65	405.6042
Observations	23	23	23	23	23

Source: E-Views 11

Key: SOCS-Social and Community Services; OREV-Oil Revenue; NOREV-Non-Oil Revenue; REER-Real Effective Exchange Rate; INFL-Inflation.

Based on the statistical summary provided in Table 1 above, the mean of SOCS is 659.41; the median value when the data is ordered is 774.77, indicating a slight right skew. The highest SOCS recorded is 1628.99 and the lowest SOCS recorded is 79.63. The data variability is 502.31, indicating significant dispersion. The positive skewness of 0.49 suggests a slight right tail; and, with a kurtosis of 2.05, the distribution is slightly platykurtic (flatter than normal). The probability of the Jarque-Bera test is 0.41 indicates the null hypothesis of normality cannot be rejected.

The average OREV is 4527.05. The median oil revenue is 4462.91, close to the mean, suggesting symmetry. The highest OREV recorded is 8878.97; while the lowest OREV recorded is 1230.85. The variability in OREV is 2015.70. The positive skewness of 0.28 suggests near symmetry; with a kurtosis value of 2.56 indicating a distribution close to normal. The probability value of the Jarque-Bera test is 0.78 strongly suggests the distribution is normal.

The mean of NOREV is 2518.91 with a median value for non-oil revenue is 2237.88, which is lower than the mean. The highest NOREV recorded is 7944.56; and, the lowest NOREV recorded is 314.48. The data variability is 1997.39, showing high dispersion. A skewness of 1.03 indicates a significant right tail; with a kurtosis of 3.63, the distribution is leptokurtic (peaked). The probability of the Jarque-Bera test is 0.11 suggests normality cannot be strongly rejected.

The average REER is 92.46; while, the median REER is 85.13, lower than the mean, indicating right skewness. The highest REER recorded is 155.75; and, the lowest REER recorded is 58.25. The variability in REER is 27.07. Skewness of 1.14 indicates a right tail; and, kurtosis of 3.30 indicates the distribution is nearly normal. The probability of the Jarque-Bera test is 0.079 suggests borderline non-normality.

The mean of INFL is 13.07; and, the median inflation rate is 12.00, indicating slight right skewness. The highest inflation rate recorded is 23.80; and, the lowest inflation rate recorded is 6.60. The data variability is 4.29, indicating moderate dispersion. The skewness value of 0.78 suggests a noticeable right tail; with a kurtosis of 3.21 indicating a distribution close to normal. The probability value of the Jarque-Bera test is 0.30 suggests normality cannot be rejected.

4.1 Stationarity Test

A unit root signifies that the data is non-stationary, implying that the statistical characteristics of the series vary over time. The ADF test is an advancement of the original D-F is capable of dealing with more intricate forms of autocorrelation. Table 2 displays the unit root test results for the individual series.

Null Hypothesis (H_0): The variable X has a unit root

Alternate Hypothesis (H_1): The variable X has no unit root

Table 2: ADF test for model variables

Variable		ADF	Prob*	
SOCS	Level	1(0)	-1.839951	0.6505
	First difference	1(1)	-3.909532	0.0302**
OREV	Level	1(0)	-2.170302	0.4826
	First difference	1(1)	-4.832770	0.0044***
NOREV	Level	1(0)	1.403654	0.9999
	Second difference	1(2)	-7.041294	0.0001***
REER	Level	1(0)	-2.113809	0.5116
	First difference	1(1)	-4.171592	0.0173**
INFL	Level	1(0)	-4.524917	0.0079***

Source: E-Views 11

Note: *, ** and *** denote significance levels at 10%, 5%, and 1% respectively.

Table 2 above summarizes the results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test for checking the stationarity of various model variables at different levels and differences. The p-value of SOCS is less than 0.05, so we reject the null hypothesis at the 5% significance level. The first difference of SOCS is stationary, indicating SOCS is I(1). The p-value of OREV is less than 0.01, so we reject the null

hypothesis at the 1% significance level. The first difference of OREV is stationary, indicating OREV is I(1). The p-value of NOREV is less than 0.01, so we reject the null hypothesis at the 1% significance level. The second difference of NOREV is stationary, indicating NOREV is I(2). The p-value of REER is less than 0.05, so we reject the null hypothesis at the 5% significance level. The first difference of REER is stationary, indicating REER is I(1). Lastly, the p-value of INFL is less than 0.01, so we reject the null hypothesis at the 1% significance level. INFL at level is stationary, indicating INFL is I(0). These results indicate that transformations (differencing) are necessary to achieve stationarity for the variables before any time series analysis like cointegration or vector autoregression (VAR) can be performed. However, in contrast, the variable INFL is already stationary and does not require differencing.

4.2 Granger Causality Test

Table 3: Granger causality test of model variables

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
OREV does not Granger Cause SOCS	21	0.54286	0.5914
SOCS does not Granger Cause OREV		0.46270	0.6377
NOREV does not Granger Cause SOCS	21	5.74656	0.0132
SOCS does not Granger Cause NOREV		1.88365	0.1842

Source: E-Views 11

The pairwise Granger causality test suggest that past values of Oil Revenue (OREV) do not significantly help predict current values of Social Spending (SOCS), as indicated by the p-value of 0.5914. Similarly, the reverse relationship from SOCS to OREV is also not significant (p-value = 0.6377). This implies that there is no strong evidence to suggest a causal relationship between OREV and SOCS in either direction. In contrast, the tests indicate that past values of Non-Oil Revenue (NOREV) do significantly help predict current values of Social Spending (SOCS), with a low p-value of 0.0132. However, the reverse relationship from SOCS to NOREV is not significant (p-value = 0.1842). This suggests that changes in Non-Oil Revenue may have a predictive effect on Social Spending, but the reverse causality is not supported by the data.

NOREV

REER

INFL

The time series plots show a clear upward trend in SOCS expenditure from 2000 to 2022, with some periods of more rapid increase. Oil revenue shows considerable volatility with noticeable peaks around 2008 and 2014. After 2014, there seems to be a downward trend with some fluctuations. Non-oil revenue exhibited a steady increase over the period, with a more pronounced rise starting around 2014. The REER shows significant fluctuations, with a peak around 2008 followed by a decline and further variations. The inflation rate shows high volatility, especially in the early 2000s. There appears to be a general downward trend with some spikes in recent years.

Table 4: Cointegration test for model variables

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.827863	90.45263	69.81889	0.0005
At most 1 *	0.674244	53.50387	47.85613	0.0134
At most 2 *	0.596680	29.95016	29.79707	0.0480
At most 3	0.278950	10.88163	15.49471	0.2189
At most 4 *	0.173972	4.013648	3.841466	0.0451

Source: E-Views 11

The cointegration test results, shows that there are three cointegrating equations, according to the Trace test, and one cointegrating equation, according to the Maximum Eigenvalue test, at the 0.05 significance level.

4.3 Test of Hypothesis

Ho₁: There is no significant effect of oil revenue (OREV) on social and community services expenditure (SOCS).

Ho₂: There is no significant effect of non-oil revenue (NOREV) on social and community services expenditure (SOCS).

Table 5: ARDL test for model variables

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
SOCS(-1)	0.624164	0.200118	3.118974	0.0075
OREV	0.028038	0.014403	1.946714	0.0719
OREV(-1)	-0.027321	0.016653	-1.640650	0.1231
NOREV	-0.013554	0.052199	-0.259667	0.7989
NOREV(-1)	0.147916	0.077797	1.901322	0.0780
REER	0.014979	1.034975	0.014473	0.9887
INFL	-6.892145	6.667168	-1.033744	0.3188
C	81.95613	196.9258	0.416178	0.6836
R-squared	0.977519	Mean dependent var		685.5263
Adjusted R-squared	0.966279	S.D. dependent var		497.8887
S.E. of regression	91.42860	Akaike info criterion		12.14428
Sum squared resid	117028.6	Schwarz criterion		12.54102
Log likelihood	-125.5871	Hannan-Quinn criter.		12.23774
F-statistic	86.96553	Durbin-Watson stat		1.419842
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: E-Views 11

The Table above shows that R² and Adjusted R² indicate a high level of fit, with the model explaining approximately 96.63% (based on Adjusted R²) of the variance in SOCS. The F-statistic is highly significant (p = 0.000000), indicating that the model is highly statistically significant. The Durbin-Watson Statistic value of 1.419842 suggests some positive autocorrelation in the residuals, though it is close to the range where it might not be a severe issue.

Interpretation of Results

The lag of SOCS is significant (p = 0.0075) and positively related to the current value of SOCS, indicating some persistence in the series.

The current value of OREV is marginally significant ($p = 0.0719$), suggesting a possible impact on SOCS. The lag of OREV is not significant ($p = 0.1231$). Thus, we fail to reject the H_{01} of no significant effect of oil revenue on social and community services expenditure.

NOREV nor NOREV(-1) is significant at conventional levels, though NOREV(-1) is close to significance ($p = 0.0780$). Thus, we fail to reject the H_{02} of no significant effect of non-oil revenue on social and community services expenditure.

The variable REER was not significant ($p = 0.9887$); and, INFL was also not significant ($p = 0.3188$).

Table 6: Heteroskedasticity test for model

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey			
F-statistic	0.501500	Prob. F(7,14)	0.8185
Obs*R-squared	4.410555	Prob. Chi-Square(7)	0.7315
Scaled explained SS	2.938675	Prob. Chi-Square(7)	0.8906

Source: E-Views 11

The Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test examines whether the variance of the residuals is constant. The p-value for the F-statistic is 0.8185, is higher than conventional significance levels (0.01, 0.05, and 0.10). Therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. The p-value for the Chi-square statistic is 0.7315, is also higher than conventional significance levels. Therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis. These indicate no significant evidence of heteroskedasticity in the residuals

Table 7: ARDL long run form and bounds test for model

Conditional Error Correction Regression				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	81.95613	196.9258	0.416178	0.6836
SOCS(-1)*	-0.375836	0.200118	-1.878070	0.0814
OREV(-1)	0.000717	0.015592	0.045965	0.9640
NOREV(-1)	0.134362	0.055167	2.435559	0.0288
REER**	0.014979	1.034975	0.014473	0.9887
INFL**	-6.892145	6.667168	-1.033744	0.3188
D(OREV)	0.028038	0.014403	1.946714	0.0719
D(NOREV)	-0.013554	0.052199	-0.259667	0.7989

Source: E-Views 11

The coefficient of SOCS(-1) is -0.375836, which is significant at the 10% level (p -value = 0.0814). This negative and significant coefficient indicates that there is an adjustment towards long-run equilibrium.

NOREV(-1) has a significant positive coefficient (0.134362) with a p -value of 0.0288, indicating that it has a significant long-term effect on SOCS.

Other variables (OREV, REER, INFL) are not significant in the long run, as indicated by their high p -values.

Table 8: F-Bounds test

F-Bounds Test			Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship	
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
Asymptotic: n=1000				
F-statistic	2.367123	10%	2.2	3.09
k	4	5%	2.56	3.49
		2.5%	2.88	3.87
		1%	3.29	4.37
Finite Sample: n=35				
Actual Sample Size	22	10%	2.46	3.46
		5%	2.947	4.088
		1%	4.093	5.532

	Finite Sample: n=30		
10%		2.525	3.56
5%		3.058	4.223
1%		4.28	5.84

Source: E-Views 11

Bounds Test for Cointegration

The F-statistic (2.367123) is below the critical values for the lower bound (I(0)) at conventional significance levels (10%, 5%, and 1%). This means we fail to reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration. The ARDL Bounds Test suggest that there is no strong evidence of a long-term cointegrating relationship between SOCS and the independent variables (OREV, NOREV, REER, and INFL). The error correction term is significant, indicating that adjustments are made towards equilibrium in the short run.

4 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first hypothesis showed a non-significant positive effect of oil revenue on social and community services expenditure. Onwuegbuna and Abodunrin (2024) finds no significant positive association between federal allocation and capital expenditure. From a different context, Oyedokun, Adeleye, and Nwabuzor (2024) exploring the relationship between tax revenue and infrastructure development in the healthcare sector of Nigeria showed a strong positive correlation between spending on health infrastructure development and certain tax types like CIT, PPT, and value-added tax. Ihugba and Njoku (2017), observed that total expenditure on social and community services did not show statistical significance but had a positive relationship with economic growth in the long run, indicating a potential link between oil revenue and social spending. Additionally, Hong (2017) studied authoritarian regimes between 1972 and 2008 revealed that oil abundance led to significantly lower levels of social spending, particularly in education and health sectors, showcasing a negative impact of oil wealth on social expenditures.

The second hypothesis showed a non-significant negative effect of non-oil revenue on social and community services expenditure. The finding aligns with such from various research papers. The study by Habeeb and Hasan (2023) discusses how oil revenues can lead to imbalances like budget deficits, affecting economic growth negatively. Furthermore, Oghuma, Eluyela, and Iyoha (2022) delve into the dynamic relationship between non-oil taxes and economic growth in Nigeria, showcasing both the positive and negative impacts of different tax revenues on GDP.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that revenue generation from oil and non-oil sources plays a crucial role in social and community services expenditure in Nigeria. Based on the above, the study makes the following recommendations in the Nigerian context:

1. **Diversification of Revenue Sources:** The Nigerian government should prioritize efforts to diversify its revenue sources beyond oil to reduce dependency on volatile oil prices. By expanding the tax base, improving tax compliance, and promoting non-oil sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and services, the government can secure stable funding for social and community services. Secondly, enhancing transparency and accountability in the management of oil revenues to prevent misappropriation and ensure that funds are allocated efficiently to priority areas.
2. **Enhanced Tax Collection and Administration:** Strengthening tax collection mechanisms, enhancing transparency, and combatting tax evasion are essential to maximize non-oil revenue mobilization. Utilizing digital tax platforms, streamlining tax procedures, and enforcing compliance measures can boost government revenue streams to support social welfare initiatives. Implementing a performance-based budgeting strategy can also improve the efficiency and effectiveness of non-oil

revenue allocations for social services. The government needs to demonstrate political will, commitment to reform, and collaboration with all stakeholders to achieve these objectives and create a more inclusive and resilient society.

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